

AMONG THE CROPS OF GRAIN ,WHEAT, BARLEY, RICE IN AGRICULTURE, MANY VOLATILE WEEDS.

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Anatation: In this article, we will give information about harmful weeds that are being fought hard in Uzbekistan and agriculture. They are considered a big problem not only in Uzbekistan, but also all over the world.

Key words: zarpechak, shumgiya, karakurmak, itkoq, Shura, olabuta, ituzum, semizot, eshakshura, parasite destroyers, microbes.

Пояснение: В этой статье мы дадим информацию о вредных сорняках, с которыми упорно борются в Узбекистане и сельском хозяйстве. Они считаются большой проблемой не только в Узбекистане, но и во всем мире.

Ключевые слова: зарпечак, шумгия, каракурмак, иткок, Шура, олабута, итузум, семизот, эшакшура, уничтожители паразитов, микробы.

Weeds, weeds — plants that people do not plant, but grow between crops and damage them, it is not advisable to grow in a certain area. Weeds cause great damage to agriculture, reducing the yield of cultivated plants. Crop losses due to weeds on a global scale are \$ 20 billion or 14.5% of the total crop, 15 — 20% of the crop of cotton and other crops in Uzbekistan. Weeds use more nutrients and moisture in the soil than ore plants with a strongly developed root system, preventing them from developing as well as accumulating high yields. For example, a well-developed Bush can grow a square area of 3-4 meters in a hummingbird soil. Parasitic weeds (zarpechak, shumgiya) are very dangerous, absorbing nutrients directly from the cultivated plant itself and killing them.

Several thousand species of weeds are known. In Uzbekistan, about 269 species are found on the territory of irrigated farming, including one-year-old weeds such as karakurmak, itkoq, Shura, olabuta, ituzum, semizot, eshakshura and many others, which from many years cause damage to crops such as qumay, ayriq, sheepchak, salomalaykum and others. According to the way of life and the structure of the underground vegetative organs, it is divided into one, two and perennial weeds. One-year weeds give seeds that thrive only once in their life. Their development lasts only one or two growing seasons. Their roots develop only in the surface layers of the Earth. Most reproduce using seeds (except for zarpechak).

This group includes 3 types of weeds:

Ephemers are annual weeds with a fast and short development cycle, the life of which ends with the onset of summer drought, there are autumn and spring forms of these (wild boars, glitters, etc.). Ephemers are distributed mainly in lalmicor crops. Annual weeds with a long growth cycle differ from ephemers in that the development cycle lasts longer and usually ends in autumn. The development of some species (spring forms) begins in early spring, when the days warm up (for example:zarpechak, ostrichin, etc.) - However, most species belong to the autumn form. Two - year weeds overwinter in this case, forming a ballbar in the first year of life. And in the second year, the stem develops, the fruit is over and dies (for example: eyelet, satonkelmas, moxobel, etc.).To lose them, a lot of effort and money is spent. Perennial weeds Bloom and fertilize several times in their life. They can also reproduce with underground organs. Depending on the structure and appearance of the underground organs, perennial weeds can be divided into several types. Arrowroot weeds have the main root and many small tubers that come out of it, as well as root hairs (for example:zurburum, sachratqi, etc.). These plants do not reproduce in a vegetative way. The small roots of the Poplar-root weed will be

strongly developed (zubtutum). Root bacilli are very well developed and grow deep into the ground, they have bacilli that develop from root shoots. Bachkis are formed from the main root of some plants, along the entire root system of some (boztican) or from the roots of special reproduction (Clover, whitefly, jinchak, etc.). Such weeds differ from others in their extreme survival. Rhizome weeds have a rhizome in horizontal creeping, underground stems that do not go deep into the ground: these are short (hummingbirds) in some and long (separated, wheatgrass) in others. Pieces of rhizome that have fallen into moistened soil have the property of growing quickly and easily. There will be an underground onion or legume of weeds with ildismeva (Wild Onion, Tulip, etc.). It is propagated mainly by seed, as well as with the help of a thistle or onion. Pinch-root weeds are pop-root, of which the upper organs of the earth grow year after year to form grass. Such weeds do not have the property of vegetative reproduction (savaghi, etc.).

Types of weeds that are not found in the territory of our republic and are at risk of spreading are called Quarantine weeds. Their distribution areas are monitored every year by employees of the on-site quarantine inspection and carry out quarantine measures to eliminate them. Identification of common natural enemies of crop pests (parasite destroyers, microbes,) and weed destroyers. To go to the bionasatory laboratories and destroy the poisonous natural enemies of weeds and the production and reproduction of larvae, eggs, hummingbirds, parasites, microbes and their carriers in the laboratory. Collect destroyers and parasites. The practice of identifying and cultivating common insect pathogens. Registration standard and quality control for bionasure tools.

Quarantine weeds spread in some regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Wormwood Ambrosia-Ambrosia artemisifolia L. It is an annual plant belonging to the Asteraceae family and outwardly resembles Wormwood. It is a plant with a branched stem, upright grower, 10 cm to 2 m high. The STEM is arrowroot, well developed, up to 4 m deep in

length. Leaf bands are well expressed, pubescent, covered with a short feather, 5 - 10 cm long. The flowers are bisexual, 5-membered, spike-shaped inflorescences of yellow color are arranged in basket-shaped inflorescences, dressing at 1-2 ends of the stem. Maternal inflorescences are placed in the leaf axils, dressing in a basket. The seed is an inverted ovoid, with wedge - shaped contractions at the ends, inside the sohta fruit there is a dressing 1 - 2 mm long with a length of 2-5 mm. The flowering and fruit dressing of the plant begins in July, August, and the seed ripens in August September. The center of origin of this weed is North America in xisoblansa, it is found in Asia, Europe, Central, South America, Australia, Russia and Uzbekistan. Wormwood Ambrosia makes 30-80 thousand pieces of seed dressing and reproduces by means of seeds. The growing season is 80-150 days. Seeds are spread by wind and seed material, River by water, ditches. It causes great damage by polluting all crops. Among these anti-weed quarantine measures, strict control of seed materials, compliance with the rules of crop rotation, fields in which weeds are scattered should be left plowed for the second year. It consists in the fact that the plantings are treated with herbicides.

The main task of the employees of the Republican quarantine inspection is to ensure that the territory of the Republic is protected from diseases that are not found inside the country, from diseases that enter the territory of the Republic through foreign countries. It is also important to be able to study them in a timely manner, limit and eliminate the spread in case of detection of New harmful sources within the country. Among the quarantine measures, it is important to know the quarantine situation of products entering and taking out inside the country. This process increases to Amala based on the examination of existing materials and laboratory examination. That is, an important production process is considered, in which the observation and laboratory examination carried out by quarantine inspectors are inextricably linked. In order to reduce the harm of microorganisms, a number of quarantine measures are being implemented in the Republic. These activities include regular control of all crops, seeds planted in it, seedlings, industrial and food products, as well as measures to eliminate them if they are identified.

Conclusion

In this article, we will give information about harmful weeds that are being fought hard in Uzbekistan and agriculture. They are considered a big problem not only in Uzbekistan, but also all over the world. In conclusion, we can say that because there is much more to do in the quarantine area. We must work hard in this area.

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